

Effective And Fun Learning Management Of Islamic Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 23, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Management,Effective And Fun Learning, Planning, Organization, Evaluation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4565525</p>	<p><i>Teaching methods improvement in school is increasingly important in globalization era and educational autonomy. There have been school management change, from centralized management into School-Based Management so that school should prioritize on the needs of students as education customers and stakeholders.Learning orientation also changed, from teacher-centered learning into student-centered learning. Teacher must be able to implement active learning that is innovative, creative, effective, fun, interactive, inspiring, challenging, and motivate students to participate actively. Moreover, teacher also has to provide chance for students to explore their talents, interests, physical and psychological development into innovative, creative, and independent activities.This paper aims to review learning plan, organization, implementation, and evaluation in a learning process. The result of the review represents that all stages of the learning management is a prerequisite of success in education system with modern learning approach. Therefore, schools and teachers should have the readiness to implement school-based management with the goal of maximizing the education quality.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning process is a complicated and complex process. A new theory of the learning process is proposed, based on the assumption that learning resembles a search programme using the branch and bound algorithm (Roberts, 2017). There are various aspects that are interrelated and affect the success or failure of learning activities. Many teachers have taught for years but the activities do not provide much positive aspects for their students' lives. On the other hand, there are teachers who are relatively new, but they have made concrete contributions for the students' progress and positive changes.

Learning as a process is strongly influenced by the teacher's role. It means that the teacher will determine whether the learning process carried out will bring maximum results as expected or not. In order to the learning process runs optimally, a strategy as general program (grand plans) must include goals, objectives, policies and resource allocation. This strategy can be implemented effectively if its management includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating. Learning is a complex process and involves various interrelated aspects. Therefore, there must be active, innovative, creative, effective, and fun learning. To realize it, learning skills or teaching skills are needed. This strategy can be implemented effectively if its management includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating (Carrinton, 2004).

Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation number 19 of 2005 concerning national education standards article 19 explains that the learning process in an education is carried out interactively, inspiratively, fun, challenging, motivating students to participate actively, as well as providing sufficient chance for initiative, creativity and independence in accordance with the students' talents, interests, physical and psychological development. Teaching skills are professional competencies that are quite complex, as an integration of various teacher competencies fully and comprehensively. As stated in Law no. 20 of 2003, learning is a process of students' interaction with educators and learning resources in a learning environment. The learning process can run optimally if a strategy which is as general program (grand plans) includes goals, objectives, policies and resource allocation. In order to implement the strategy effectively, there must be learning management which includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating.

Result And Discussion Education Management

Many opinions that provide limits about management. One of them is "Management refers to activities (and often the group of people) involved in the four general functions, planning, organization, leading and coordinating of resources" (Namara, 2004). Sudjana (2002: 12) explains that management means all activities carried out by a person or more in a group or organization or institution to achieve the stated organization or institution goals. The nature of management according to Hoyle (Bush & Coleman, 2000: 4) is "a continuous

process through which members of an organization seek to co-ordinate their activities and use their resources in order to fulfill the various tasks of the organization as efficient as possible”.

Management has an important position in every institution because management is closely related to others in determining or setting goals. In other words, management is not only to identify, analyze or set goals carefully but also to place human resources and other resources effectively. In this case, almost all human activities, whether in offices, hospitals, banks, or in educational institutions require management activities. Management has universal principles. Management activities are always concerned with efforts to achieve certain goals that have been set effectively and efficiently. In terms of ‘effective and efficient’, Drucker (in Schoderbek, 1988: 22) states "effectiveness is the foundation of success; efficiency is a minimum condition for survival after success has been achieved. Efficiency is concerned with doing things right”. Effectiveness is doing the right things. Effectiveness is the foundation for achieving success and efficiency is the minimum resource used to achieve that success. Efficiency refers to doing things well, while effectiveness is about the work done in right way. Thus, if it is described in more detail, then management activities can be seen in the following table.

Source: Sugiyono (2000)

There is no fundamental difference between management in one field with management in another because all management activities are related to efforts to achieve a certain goal. Therefore, the management principles of one field with another is the same. The difference is the field concern. It can be stated that the principles of management are universal, applicable in all fields and organizations including educational organizations. It can also be understood that resources generally consist of: (1) man, (2) money, (3) materials, (4) machines, (5) methods, (6) market, (7) minute. Each of these resources has its own function.

Leadership quality will greatly affect the performance of an organization, whether it is educational organization or other organizations. Based on these conditions, the leader or manager plays a main role in achieving the institution goals effectively and efficiently. According to Adair (in Boylan, 2002,) to support the success of an organization, managers must understand first about the organization internal and external conditions. More tips from Adair are as follow.

1. clear difference between "managing" and "leading"
2. actually 50% of performance within teams comes from self (cf. Mc Gregor's Theory Y) but the other 50% comes from quality of leadership.
3. leaders should be good at inspiring others: this depends on their own and their ability to communicate and share that effort and commitment with the rest of the team.
4. concept and training methods of "Action-Central Leadership" and "Action-Centered Leadership" (both known as "ACL"), based on three overlapping circles; Task, Team and Individual

Based on the description above, it can also be seen that the manager is the spearhead of a team to achieve the stated organizational goals. According to Belbin (in Boylan, 2002), some basic points must be done by leaders in the team are:

1. something must be built based on diversity because the values in the team vary from one person to another
2. pay attention and explore the talents of subordinates because not all of them have special abilities
3. develop and support the growth of personal power
4. have mission creativity
5. give delegation of tasks to the right person.

In the context of educational organizations, some things that must be done by educational managers is to improve the education quality. That is curriculum. Doll (1982: 209-210) suggests several things, including:

1. help the people of the school community define their educational goals and objectives
2. facilitate the teaching-learning process, to develop great effect on teaching

3. build a productive organizational unit
4. create a climate for growth and emergence of leadership
5. provide adequate resources for effective teaching.

Learning Management

Smith (in Mappa, 1994: 11) argues that the term "learning" can be used to show: (1) acquisition and mastery about something, (2) counseling and explanation about someone's experience meaningor, (3) a process of testing organized ideas that are relevant to the problem. In other words, the term 'learning' is used to describe an outcome, process or function. Knowles (in Mappa, 1994: 12) believes that "learning" is a process that seeks a change in behavior, shaped or controlled. Furthermore, it was stated that learning is a change that can produce results.

Sudjana (2002: 3) says that the learning process is the students' activities to learn, while educators play a role to help students in conducting learning activities. Furthermore, Sudjana stated four types of learning, namely skills learning, cognitive learning, attitude learning and problem solving learning. Skills learning consists of productive skills, technical skills, physical skills and intellectual skills. Types of cognitive learning include information learning, concept learning and principle learning. Then, type of attitude learning includes efforts to form the students' attitudes through the stages of learning activities. Meanwhile, the type of problem solving learning is based on phenomena in the field by considering problem solving efforts.

In contrast, Battencourt's (in Harvest, 2001: 7) defines learning as a form of self-learning. Furthermore, Harvest included Von Glaserfeld's opinion which said that learning is helping someone think correctly by letting him think for himself. If someone has a good way of thinking, it means that their way of thinking can be used to deal with a new phenomenon and will be able to find solutions in dealing with other problems.

According to Brown (in Pringgowidagda, 2002: 20), learning is defined by the process of showing or helping someone to learn how, do something, give instructions, guide in learning something, give knowledge, cause someone to know or understand. Furthermore, Oemarjati (1983: 59) says that learning is a teaching and learning process in a formal environment that aims to develop students' potential in accordance with students' abilities regarding intelligence, honesty, skills, recognition of abilities and limits and will recognize and maintain their self-respect. In other words, each learning implies an educational effort aimed at building students' character. Students who are actively involved in the learning process are characterized by two activities, namely doing and active in thinking. The real students' action in learning is the result of thinking involvement on the object of learning. Experience as a result of student actions is further developed in the reflective direction (Suparno, 2002: 137).

Based on the opinions above, then it can be said that learning is the process of using ideas by linking experiences that students have had with something that has been faced so that students are guided to find their own experiences that can change themselves so that students can feel the benefits and changes that are had happened to him. Learning activities occur through interaction between students and educators. Learning activities are carried out by students and learning activities are carried out by educators. This activity is carried out deliberately in order to achieve a learning goal. Learning objectives are related to the students' changes. They include aspects of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and aspirations. Through learning, a person can change, from 'not knowing' to 'knowing', 'not clever' to 'smart', 'not good' to be 'good' and 'not able' to be 'able'.

The definitions that have been mentioned can be formulated that learning is a process that begins with the acquisition of information as the basis for changes in behavior that can produce results or something new. The learning that happens at school is a learning done by students so that behavior changes occur based on information received to achieve an outcome. Teachers as managers in the learning process in the classroom are responsible for integrating all forms of elements in the classroom. As a manager, the teacher must try to coordinate activities towards the achievement of the classroom organization system objectives in order to realize students' behaviour changes according to the goals set.

Good and Brophy (in Jones, 2001: 3) said, "The findings show that teachers who approach classroom management as a process of establishing and maintaining effective learning environments tend to be more successful teachers who place more emphasis on the roles as authority figures on disciplinarians ". The findings show that teachers in the classroom as a process of developing and maintaining an effective learning environment tend to be more successful than teachers who place themselves as authority figures in their teaching. Furthermore, Mc Caslin and Good (in Jones, 2001: 3) stated "Classroom management can and should do more than predictable obedience elites; indeed, it can and should be one vehicle for the enhancement of student self-understanding, self-evaluation, and the internalization of self-control." Then Arikunto (1999: 1) says that learning management is the administration, arrangement of a learning activity by showing an activity that contains the process of mastery, skills and attitudes.

The learning process occurs in a person to make a relationship between stimulants and reactions or one reactions to another. Factors that influence learning here need attention from people who are directly involved in

the learning process, especially teachers who are directly and responsible for the process of implementing learning in the classroom. Thus, learning management can be done intensively.

Jensen (in DePorter, Reardon & Singer-Nourie, 2000) said that a satisfying resource for teachers is to provide background and strategies to improve learning and make the teaching process more enjoyable. Everything that is done in learning management (every interaction with students, every learning design, every instructional method) is built on the principle of Bringing Their World to Our World and Delivering our world to Their World (DePorter, and Singer Nourie (2000: 6). The principle implies that learning is carried out by linking what is taught with an event, thought or feeling obtained from students' home, social and academic life. After the link is formed, the teacher gives students an understanding of the world, for example new vocabulary, mental models, formulas, etc. Finally, with broad understanding and deep mastery, students can bring what they learn into their world and apply it to new situations.

If the learning concepts are related to management concepts, it can provide an understanding that learning management is an activity of planning, organizing, mobilizing and monitoring that takes place in learning to make behavior changes based on information received. Reigeluth and Garfinkel (1994) describe that teachers as facilitators and education managers. This role requires a resource-based system, the use of the power of new tools related to technological progress rather than being based on teachers.

The teacher's professional task is to carry out teaching activities, and then responses from the students is called learning. The interaction of these two activities, teaching and learning in the classroom, is called the teaching process. The teacher conducts teaching activities in the classroom. According to Davis (1991: 35), the teacher's role as a manager in the teaching process are:

1. Planning. It is to set the goals of teaching and learning process;
2. Organizing, namely connecting or combining all teaching and learning resources in achieving goals effectively and efficiently;
3. leading. It is motivating students to be ready to receive subject matter,
4. Supervising. It is evaluating whether the work or teaching and learning activities achieve teaching objectives. Therefore there must be a teaching evaluation process, so that the results achieved.

The teacher's role as a manager is directing students to conduct learning activities in the context of behavior change (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) towards maturity. Effective learning only exists in effective schools. Therefore, the core of school activities is effective teaching and learning to produce graduates who have good personalities. For this reason, it is necessary to optimize the function of the components to achieve effective school quality. Effective schools have several main elements, namely: 1) leadership, 2) school environment, 3) curriculum, 4) classroom teaching and management, 5) assessment and evaluation.

According to Hoban (in Heinich, 1970: 106), management of learning includes the interrelationship of various events, not only learning events in the learning process, but also logistical, sociological and economic factors. It covers all events because learning management systems are concerned with educational technology where technology is an integrated and complex organization of people, machines, ideas, procedures and management. So theory of learning, teaching, learning management are pure, applied science and systems. Learning theory crosses teaching theory in which various factors are linked into the learning management system.

As managers in learning, teachers need better collaboration and working groups among students, including cooperative learning and long-term tutorials rather than the traditional point of view that places student collaboration sufficiently as necessary. The main problem of education is learning because learning is a major process of human survival. The main problem of education is not only learning, but management of learning. Learning and management are terms that are not the same, more than learning and teaching. So it can be said that the problem of teaching and learning is part of the learning problems (Hoban in Heinich, 1970).

In book *Instructional Design Theories and Models*, Reigeluth (1994: 8) explained that: "Instructional, improving and applying of managing the use of an implemented instructional program". It means that management is improvement and implementation of the teaching programs management.

Learning management is broader than merely educational administration because this activity includes a teaching program in an educational institution. Learning management is the process of helping students to achieve knowledge, skills, abilities and understanding of the world around them. The consequence is that learning management creates opportunities for how students learn and what students learn. In other words, learning management raises the question, how can they learn, what do they learn and where do they learn it? To achieve this goals, effective management strategies are needed in the classroom, especially organizing the learning and teaching activities. Finally, the teacher has a readiness to teach and students are prepared to learn.

In terms of learning management, the concepts of learning strategies and teaching styles used by teachers will be examined to determine success in achieving teaching objectives. The benefits of learning management are as professional activities in using and maintaining units of teaching programs that are implemented. Learning / teaching management discipline is related to efforts to produce knowledge about various management procedures. The optimal combination of various procedures and situations where the

management model runs optimally. It means learning management is the process of utilizing all interacting components (teaching resources) to achieve the objectives of the teaching program.

Learning management functions, namely: planning teaching, organizing teaching, leadership, and evaluation in the process of teaching and learning activities or *Kegiatan Belajar Mengajar*(KBM). In carrying out the management function referred to, a teacher must utilize teaching resources (learning resources) found in the classroom and outside the classroom.

The success of the teaching process carried out will be determined by the utilization of appropriate teaching resources to achieve the goals. Teaching resources that are carefully selected and prepared will be able to achieve the objectives: (1) Motivating students by increasing their attention and encouraging attraction towards a subject, (2) Involving students with more meaningful experiences, (3) Personality formation for each individual in teaching, (4) Explaining and illustrating content and displaying various skills, (5) Contributing to forms of attitude and developing appreciation, (6) Providing opportunities for self-analysis, performance and behavior personally (Kemp, 1993).

Various teaching resources that can be used by teachers in learning include: (1) Guest speakers or a person who has qualifications in a particular field that can motivate students about various information, (2) Objects related to subject matter, (3) Textbooks, (4) Various writings / papers, diagrams, outlines that can serve the purpose of teaching during the process of teaching activities, (5) Use of pictures, (6) Records of lectures, etc., (7) CD-ROM that provides a lot of information that can be accessed and controlled on a computer, (8) Photo CDs containing recorded images from films and can be accessed using a computer, (9) Overhead transparency, (10) Films, video tapes, etc. There are several general procedures for using and selecting resources in teaching programs, namely:

1. Choose on the basis of what is easy to get (things provided by the teaching field, and what is easy to get or use).
2. Choose on the basis of what is familiar and well understood by the instructor and is very enjoyable (which is liked and often used in learning units).
3. Choose on the basis of teaching objectives where there are guidelines that can be followed in selecting and using learning resources (Kemp, 1993).

According to Bastian (2002), the utilization of educational technology has been popular in the community. The growth of the industry supporting education is also growing, not only focused on information technology, but also opportunities for local industries to produce a variety of teaching aids and simulations. The more technology is utilized in the world of education, the more open opportunities for the creative work of the educated community. The next concrete form is that in order to move towards an educational revolution with the advantages of supporting technology. Careful consideration is needed from an expert team to determine the right strategies and choices. However the limitations and obstacles in using equipment, services and ease of learning resources must be overcome by the teacher. What is important in the use of learning resources is consistent in helping the teaching process both students and teachers. For that reason, successful teaching and goals can be achieved optimally.

Active and Fun Learning Strategy

In the world of education, strategy is defined as a plan, method, or series of activities designed to achieve a particular educational goal (Davies, 1986). Thus, learning strategies can be interpreted as a plan that contains a series of activities designed to achieve certain educational goals.

There are two things that should be observed from the above understanding. First, the learning strategy is an action plan (series of activities) including the use of methods and the use of various resources / strengths in learning. It means that the preparation of a new strategy until the process of preparing a work plan has not yet reached action. Second, strategies are arranged to achieve certain goals. That is, the direction of all strategy-making decisions is goal planning. Thus, the preparation of learning steps, utilization of various facilities and learning resources are all directed to achieve goals. Therefore, before determining a strategy, it is necessary to formulate clear goals that can be measured for success because the goal is the spirit in implementing a strategy.

Kemp (1993) explains that the learning strategy is a learning activity that must be done by teachers and students so that learning objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently. In line with the opinion above, Dick & Reiser (1989) also mentioned that the learning strategy is a set of learning materials and procedures that are used together to produce learning outcomes for students. How the effort to implement the plan that has been arranged in real activities can achieve the objectives is called method. It means, the method is used to realize the strategy set. Thus, one learning strategy can use several methods. For example, to implement an expository strategy, the lecture method can be used as well as the question and answer method or even discussion by utilizing available resources including using learning media. Therefore, the strategy is different from the method. Strategy shows the planning to achieve something, while the method is a way that can be used to implement the strategy. In other words, strategy is a plan of operation achieving something while method is a way in achieving something.

Another term that has similarities with strategy is the approach. Actually, the approach is different from the strategy and method. Approach can be interpreted as a starting point or perspective on the learning process. The term approach refers to the view about the occurrence of a process that is still very general in nature. Therefore, the learning strategies and methods used can be sourced or dependent on certain approaches. Killen R (1998) for example notes that there are two approaches in learning, namely teacher-centered approaches and student-centered approaches. The teacher-centered approach involves direct learning strategies, deductive learning or expository learning. Meanwhile, student-centered learning approaches involves discovery and inquiry learning strategies and inductive learning strategies.

In addition to learning strategies, methods and approaches, there are also other terms that are sometimes difficult to distinguish, namely teaching techniques and tactics. Teaching techniques and tactics are a translation of the learning method. Technique is the way someone does in order to implement a method. Tactics are a person's style of carrying out a particular technique or method. Thus, tactics are more individual. The estuary of the proper functioning of learning management is effective learning. It means, teacher creates effective teaching and in terms of learning, they create effective learning. According to Joyce and Weil (1996: 11), "A successful teacher is teaching students how to have information in a conversation and make it their own. Whereas effective learners are forming information, ideas and wisdom from their teachers and using learning resources effectively".

Here, the main role in teaching is to create strong learning. The point is the learning process is understood as structuring the environment in which students can interact and learn how to learn. However, many factors are related to the effectiveness of teaching. To achieve active learning, one important aspect is the method problem used by the teacher in creating an atmosphere of active learning. In fact, there is no one learning method that is the best when compared to the others. It means, each method has advantages and disadvantages. In this context, each learning method that helps students carry out activities by constructing their knowledge that they learn well can be said to be a method that encourages active learning. However, just a few methods is not enough to encourage students to learn actively. One of them is the discovery method with an emphasis on the scientific method framework.

Suparno (2002) argues that in applying the discovery method, students are trained to be accustomed to making observations, making hypotheses, generating predictions, testing hypotheses, solving problems, looking for answers themselves, using events, researching, dialoguing, reflecting, expressing questions and expressing ideas during the process of forming a new knowledge construction. Based on the description above, it is clear that the learning process using the lecture method, where the teacher dominates the conversation while students are forced or even forced to sit, listen and take notes is not recommended. The lecture method must be reduced even abandoned. Of course this new paradigm encourages the active students require teachers to change their perspective on learning. In preparation for teaching, teachers think more / focus on the creation of (new) experiences for students so they can develop their knowledge.

The teacher can determine or choose the right material / learning material so that with an understanding of the (correct) concepts that are formed by students, it allows them to relate them to previous understanding and open opportunities to seek and find understanding of new concepts. With the creation of such understanding, the teacher has empowered his students. The teacher is not busy gathering and ultimately giving as much knowledge as possible to students, while they do not know what they are being given to them. Since the effort to create experience must be authentic, not made up, the experience allows students to be totally involved both physically and mentally. That experience must be a part of his life through which students gain new understanding and knowledge.

The success of a teacher in implementing learning is not determined by one factor but it is influenced by various internal and external factors in the school. Urlick, et al (1981: 48) argue that there are three teachers treatments that must take if they want to be more successful in teaching, namely: "(1) They are well organized in their planning (2) They communicate effectively with their students, and (3) They have high expectations to their students. " Teachers who want to succeed are required to make good planning, be skilled in effective communication (the message conveyed can be understood correctly by students), and strive with sincerity and high expectations so that students have high achievements.

In this context, support is needed for the use of new technology for education. One of the policies in the development of multimedia infrastructure in the form of large-capacity and high-speed broadband infrastructure is intended to function as an information superhighway (an informant). This main information tunnel infrastructure is the most important infrastructure to support multimedia applications that can be utilized in terms of distance education, remote laboratories, electronic libraries to other services such as remote health services, electronic banking, online transactions and others (Bastian, 2002: 79). In the perspective of active learning, our brain really does not function like a tape recorder directly records what is there. But the information that comes is usually questioned first. At least the questions are as follows:

1. has I heard or seen this information before?
2. where is this complete information? What can I do with it?

3. can I assume that this information is as ideally as I heard and saw yesterday or a few months ago? (Silberman, 1996)

However, as an indicator of how dynamic learning is, the human brain does not simply receive information, but it processes it. To process information effectively, the brain helps to reflect externally and internally. If we discuss information with others and if we invite questions, our brains can do a better job than learning. It can be said that learning will captivate students when they are instructed the following things:

- 1) convey information in their language,
- 2) give an example,
- 3) introduce it in various directions and circumstances,
- 4) see the relationship between information and facts or other ideas,
- 5) make a connection between information and facts or other ideas,
- 6) makes its use in various ways,
- 7) pay attention to some of the information consequences, and
- 8) state the difference with other information.

Learning is teaching according to principles, procedures and designs so that the goal of changing children's behavior is achieved. Meanwhile, active learning by students is learning that involves all physical and psychological elements to optimize the development of children's potential. Therefore, effective active learning is one that fulfills multi-purpose, multi-method, multi-media / source and children's self-development. The use of strategies and methods of active learning in schools is actually a positive step of appreciation for the children nature as active people who need guidance towards goals that are tailored to the psychological, spiritual, intellectual, morality, social and pragmatic demands of children's lives in the present and the future.

Active learning in schools is driven as optimally as possible in order to make teaching effective. The role of professional teachers is even greater in anticipating all opportunities for active learning in this era. With the increasingly broad source of knowledge information, the use of multiple media / sources, multiple methods to achieve integrated goals for the development of maximum potential, the teachers need to be more proactive in seeking innovative teaching methods.

The professional awareness from teachers is needed with the improvement in the social status of teachers today. This needs must be balanced with seriousness and improvement efforts in the learning process at school. Active learning that is rooted in constructivism in learning needs to be a real concern of the teacher at all times, especially the growing expectations of parents for children's education quality. Schools are expected to be able to create children who have superior attitudes, skills and knowledge optimally in facing and filling their future with life skills so that children become useful human beings, not become unemployed.

According to Ulrich (1981: 19), to make schools effective, all educational institution resources must be directed towards making learning efficient, superior and effective. For that reason, the role of the teacher is crucial for the formation of an effective learning atmosphere because the teacher who plans, implements and evaluates the learning. According to Piskurich (2000), effective learning is associated with a number of time effectiveness processes. Learning designs will provide benefits and help choices in more effective ways to present learning content that can be interpreted as things that become very easy ways for learners.

In this context, instructional design helps teachers understand what is learned and decides on a good method for learning a subject. It is added that in the classroom, it may be in the laboratory or simulation or even in training that is directly in the real world by using work tools so that the learner immediately does his work. So effective learning is determining the best way for the learners to learn based on the content they needs to learn and whether they will do their works with new knowledge after they join the learning process.

CONCLUSION

In his position as a manager, the teacher makes learning plans that include efforts to: (1) analyze tasks, (2) identify training / learning needs, (3) write learning objectives. In this way, a teacher will be able to predict the teaching assignments that he will perform. Organizing learning involves four activities, namely: (1) choosing the right tactic tool, (2) choosing the right learning aid or audio visual, (3) choosing the class size (the right number of students), (4) choosing the right and appropriate strategy for communicating complex rules, procedures and teaching. Class management deals with two main activities, namely: (1) management relating to students, (2) management relating to physical (rooms, furniture, learning tools). The implementation of a good teaching and learning process uses active learning strategies. The strategy must be able to lead students to achieve learning competence and able to shape the broad-minded students' character. Evaluation is done by the teacher through midterm tests, end-semester tests, assignments, assessing through face-to-face in the learning process, and evaluating attitudes outside of classroom learning. These are done based on technique guidelines involving cognitive, affective and psychomotor test scoring.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto. S. 1999. *Classroom and Student Management*. Jakarta: Rajawali Press.
- Bastian. A.R. 2002. *Education Reform*. Yogyakarta: Lappera Pustaka Utama.
- Boylan, P. 2002. *Introduction to the Theoretical and Philosophical Basic of Modern Managemen*.

- Bush, T. & Coleman, M. 2000. *Leadership and Strategic Management in Education*. London: Paul Chapman Publishing.
- Carrington, Gill. (2004). Supervision as a reciprocal learning process. *Educational psychology in practice*, 20(1), 31-42.
- Davis, I.K. 1991. *Learning Management*. Jalarta: CV. Rajawali.
- Depdiknas. 2003. *National Education System Law*. No. 20 of 2003. Jakarta.
- DePorter, N., Reardon, M., & Singer-Nourie, S. 2000. *Quantum Teaching*. (translated by Ary Nilandari) Bandung: PT Mizan Pustaka. (Original Book published in 1999).
- Dick, W. & Reiser, R. 1989. *Planning Effective Instruction*. Amerika: Allyn and Bacon.
- Doll, E.R. 1982. *Curriculum Improvement, Decision Making & Process*. Boston: Atlantic A.
- Heinich, R., et al. 1996. *Instructional Media and Technologies for Learning*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Hole, Y., & Snehal, P. & Bhaskar, M. (2018). Service marketing and quality strategies. *Periodicals of engineering and natural sciences*, 6 (1), 182-196.
- Jones, F. 2001. *Seating Arrangements & Assignments, A Classroom Management*. Article. Retrieved from <http://www.educationworld.com>. P.3.
- Jones, V.F. & Jones, L.S. 2001. *Comprehensive Classroom Management: Creating Communities Of Support and Solving Problems*. Needham Hights: A Pearson Education Company.
- Joyce, B & Weil, M. 1996. *Model of Teaching*. London: Allyn Bacon.
- Kemp, J.E, dkk. 1993. *Designing Effective Instruction*. New York: Macmillan.
- Killen, R. 1998. *Effective Teaching Strategies: Lesson from Research and Practice*, Second Edition. Australia: Social Science Press.
- Knowless, M. 1979. *The Adult Learner: A Neglected Species*. Houston USA: Gulf Publishing Company.
- Mappa, S. & Basleman, A, 1994. *Adult Learning Theory*. Jakarta: Dirjen Dikti.
- Mulyasa, E. 2005. *Become a Professional Teacher, Creating Creative and Fun Learning*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Namara, Mc. 2004. *Introduction to management*. Retrieved from http://www.managementhelp.org/mng_thry.htm.
- Oemarjati, B. 1983. *Indonesian Literature Teaching and Literature Appreciation Development at the Indonesian Language Congress III*. Jakarta: Pusat Pembinaan dan Pengembangan Bahasa.
- Panen, P., Dina Mustafa, & Mestika Sekarwinahyu. 2001. *Constructivism in Learning*. Jakarta: PAU-PPAI Universitas Terbuka.
- Peraturan Pemerintah (Government Regulation) RI No. 19 of 2005 about National Education Standard.
- Piskurich, G. M. 2000. *Rapid Instructional Design*. San Fransisco: Jossey Bass.
- Pringgowidagda, S. 2002. *Language Mastery Strategy*. Yogyakarta: Adicita.
- Reigeluth & Garfinkel. 1994. *System Change in Education*. New Jersey: Publication E. Cliffs.
- Roberts, Peter. (1983). A theory of the learning process. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 34(1), 71-79.
- Schoderbek, P.P., Coster, R.A., & Aplin, J.C. 1988. *Management*. Orlando: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich Inc.
- Silberman, M.L. 1996. *Active Learning: 101 Cara Belajar Aktif*. Bandung: Nusamedia.
- Stoner, J.A.F & Freeman, R.E. 2000. *Management*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall International Editions.
- Sudjana, D. 2002. *Management of Education Programs for Out-of-School Education and Human Resources Development*. Bandung: Falah Production.
- Sugiyono. 2000. *Educational Management Perspective*. Handout of *Manajemen Pluralis* Subject, Not Published, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.
- Suparno, P, et.al. 2002. *Education Reform: A Recommendation*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- Undang-undang Republik Indonesia No. 20 of 2003 about National Education System and its Explanation. Jogjakarta: Media Wacana.
- Urlich, D.C. 1980. *Teaching Strategies*. Massachusset: Heath and Company.

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